

Benchmark evaluation for a single frequency continuous wave OPO seeded pulsed dye amplifier for high-resolution laser spectroscopy

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ABSTRACT

The study of the atomic spectrum via resonant laser excitation provides access to underlying effects caused by the nuclear structure, which is of special interest in short-lived radioisotopes produced at Isotope Separator On-Line (ISOL) facilities. Current implementations of resonant laser ionization techniques often limit the extraction of the nuclear observables due to the low spectral resolution of the pulsed laser systems deployed. Several high-resolution spectroscopy techniques demand spectral widths in the order of hundreds of MHz and below. A proven solution to reduce this linewidth is the pulsed amplification of a narrow-band continuous wave (cw) laser. This work presents the demonstration of a pulsed dye amplifier seeded by a commercially available cw Optical Parametric Oscillator (OPO). The performance of this system was compared with competing setups using a cw dye laser seed source as well as a frequency mixing technique using a combination of an injection-locked titanium:sapphire (Ti:Sa) and a Nd:YVO₄ laser. Spectral bandwidths of the systems were measured using a high finesse Fabry-Perot Interferometer, resulting in comparable optical linewidths between 140 to 156 MHz at a wavelength of 328 nm for the different laser setups. Suitability for on-line experiments was validated by performing high-resolution spectroscopy of radioactive silver isotopes in the Collinear Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy (CRIS) experiment at the Isotope Separator On-Line Device (ISOLDE), at the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN). The quality of the hyperfine spectra was similar for the dye and the OPO seed and the deduced hyperfine splitting was in good agreement with literature, while the frequency mixing technique exhibited less precise results attributed to the frequency instabilities and mode-hops of the single-mode Nd:YVO₄ laser.

Keywords: optical parametric oscillator, narrow linewidth, laser ionization spectroscopy

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1. INTRODUCTION

Access to nuclear structures is provided through high-resolution studies of the atomic spectrum. Interactions of the nuclear ground state properties with the electronic shell induce small perturbations in the atomic level structure, known as the hyperfine structure (HFS) and the isotope shift (IS). Precise measurements of these effects allow the extraction of the nuclear spin I , the magnetic dipole moment μ_I , the electric quadrupole moment Q_s and changes in mean square charge radii $\delta \langle r^2 \rangle$ from isotope to isotope, all of which are closely related to the nucleus' microscopic configuration and its shape.¹ Atomic transitions of the valence electrons are in the range of a few eV, which are accessible with lasers. A very successful laser spectroscopy technique to study exotic isotopes is collinear resonance ionization spectroscopy² (CRIS). It is based on efficient resonant excitation of individual hyperfine components using a narrow-band pulsed laser and subsequent selective resonant laser ionization of the isotope of interest, whilst minimizing the Doppler and pressure broadening by collinearly overlapping a fast atom beam with the laser beam. This technique is mainly performed with pulsed lasers since they can provide sufficiently high power densities as needed for efficient ionization and in addition also for single-pass nonlinear frequency conversion.³

Although dye lasers still serve as a popular and frequently used system in the field of laser spectroscopy,^{2,4-6} the degeneration or aging of most dyes and the use of solvents, which are both flammable or toxic, are prominent disadvantages⁷ that discourage their use. Depending on the dye, and to a lesser degree the solvent, the fundamentally achievable wavelength covers a range of 370 to 900 nm, considering pump options at 532 nm and 355 nm and using about 30 different dyes.⁷ On the other hand, there are solid-state laser systems at hand today, which are a more convenient alternative to dye lasers in terms of handling. However, often the tuning range of such systems is limited to only a few to tens of nanometers. Exclusively solid-state systems based on titanium:sapphire (Ti:Sa) crystals can provide an exceptionally wide tuning range from 680 to 1000 nm, which makes Ti:Sa lasers the most commonly used systems for numerous applications in laser spectroscopy.

For high-resolution spectroscopy, the optical linewidth should be low enough to resolve the atomic lines up to the HFS but should not be (much) narrower than the resolution-limiting effect in the specific experimental setup for maximization of efficiency.⁸ In a fast beam collinear geometry, the resonance peak linewidth is in the order of 40-70 MHz,³ which is sufficient to resolve the HFS in most elements. The generation of pulsed laser light with an optical linewidth, measured as the full width at half maximum (FWHM), of less than 50 MHz has been reported⁹ by pulsed dye amplification (PDA) of a cw dye laser beam, and in the order of 20 MHz¹⁰ by injection-locking of a Ti:Sa with a narrow-linewidth cw Ti:Sa. With both methods, the final emitted pulse is limited by the width of the Fourier transform of the laser pulse, at the cost of rather challenging experimental setups.

In this work, a different approach is used to produce narrow-band laser pulses by means of a PDA of a tunable cw single-mode optical parametric oscillator (OPO). This new system is based on a commercially available C-WAVE OPO by HÜBNER Photonics (model: C-WAVE GTR) and a home-made PDA. As a benchmark evaluation for the suitability of this system, pulsed light at 328 nm is produced by three different laser systems: the new OPO based PDA setup (1) and a cw single-frequency ring dye laser amplified by PDA (2), both with subsequent single-pass frequency doubling, as well as an injection-locked Ti:Sa laser seeded by a cw single-frequency ring Ti:Sa laser, which is sum-frequency mixed with a pulsed 532 nm single longitudinal mode Nd:YVO₄ laser to reach the UV spectral range.³ High-resolution spectroscopy on silver is performed at the CRIS experiment at ISOLDE, CERN, using the three laser setups in comparison. It must be noted that this wavelength in the UV region is particularly difficult to obtain whilst maintaining power stability and a narrow optical linewidth.^{7,11,12}

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

High-resolution spectroscopy on bunched ion beams of silver was performed at the CRIS setup at CERN-ISOLDE.¹⁵ Laser ionization was carried out along the three-step excitation scheme shown in Fig. 1, and laser spectroscopy was performed by scanning the transition from the $4d^{10}5s\ 2S_{1/2}$ ground state to the $4d^{10}5p\ 2P_{3/2}$ excited state at 328 nm. The three alternative laser setups utilized to produce the first excitation step are described in the next subsection. A frequency-doubled Z-cavity Ti:Sa pumped at 532 nm was used for the second excitation step at 421 nm, and the ionization step was induced using a non-resonant transition to the continuum

Figure 1: The three-step excitation scheme applied to ionize silver in these experiments. Atom from its ground state is excited by step-wise absorption of three photons at 328nm, 421nm, and 532nm, resulting in the total excitation energy of 9.052 eV exceeding the ionization potential $IP=7.576$ eV, and a ground state hyperfine splitting of 1977 MHz¹³ and 37 MHz¹⁴ for the excited state.

at 532 nm. The lasers were synchronized at a repetition rate of 1 kHz. The absolute laser wavelength at each frequency step was recorded in the visible region with a WSU-2 wavemeter from HighFinesse GmbH.¹⁶

2.1 Laser systems

The first laser system, the OPO PDA setup, shown in Fig. 2a, consisted of a tunable single-mode cw OPO model C-WAVE GTR from HÜBNER Photonics.¹⁷ This system relies on a sequence of two nonlinear processes taking place within periodically poled crystals. The primary OPO process, pumped at 780 nm, gives a fundamental wavelength of 1312 nm, and the subsequent conversion of this output generates 656 nm by resonant frequency doubling. The cw laser light emitted by this system is then passing the PDA, which uses an ethanol solution of 4-dicyanomethylene-2-methyl-6-(p-dimethylaminostyryl)-4H-pyran (DCM) laser dye with a concentration of 0.450 g/l and 0.300 g/l in the preamplifier and main amplifier, respectively. This dye amplifier was pumped using the 532 nm output from a Nd:YVO₄ laser (PXn200-2-GF-SLM). Subsequently, the output after amplification is frequency doubled in a single-pass second harmonic generation (SHG) stage to obtain pulsed light at 328 nm.

The frequency was scanned by tuning the OPO system using the proprietary AbsoluteLambda™ algorithm by HÜBNER Photonics. AbsoluteLambda™ is based on a closed-loop feedback, measuring the actual wavelength around 656 nm with the WSU-2 wavemeter, and feeding back a control signal which acts on the internal reference cavity of the OPO system. To ensure single-mode operation across the whole tuning range of the OPO, a combination of a Fabry-Pérot etalon with a birefringent filter element is used in the OPO cavity.

The second laser, the dye PDA setup, shown in Fig. 2b, consisted of a cw dye laser (Sirah Matisse-DS) amplified by a PDA, the same as the one deployed for the OPO setup, and also in a similar way frequency doubled to generate the 328 nm pulsed light. To make the change between the OPO and dye laser, a common beam path was shared, with the use of a flip-mirror, starting at the fiber coupling to supply the cw light to the PDA system. The frequency was scanned using the Matisse Commander software.

Finally, the third laser, the sum frequency generation (SFG) setup, consisted of an injection-locked ring cavity Ti:Sa laser based on the design originally developed at the University of Mainz,¹⁸ seeded by a cw Ti:Sa laser (Sirah Matisse TS), producing pulsed light at 856 nm. In the SFG stage, using a non-linear crystal, it is mixed

(a) OPO seeded PDA: OPO PDA setup.

(b) Dye seeded PDA: dye PDA setup.

(c) Sum frequency generation (SFG): SFG setup.

Figure 2: Schematic diagrams of each of the laser systems, used for the production of the first excitation step. (a) The tunable cw OPO seeding the PDA. The OPO system employs a two-stage design with cascaded SHG of the primary OPO output. The initial red line depicts the pump laser beam at 780 nm, and dark-red and brown beams represent the signal (1312 nm) and the idler beam (1923 nm), respectively. The exiting orange arrow visualizes the SHG beam originating from the frequency doubling of the signal, at 656 nm. After fiber coupling, the cw light is pulsed amplified within two amplifier stages. A subsequent SHG stage provides the 328 nm pulse. (b) The cw dye laser at 656 nm, pulsed amplified by the PDA, and subsequently frequency doubled. (c) The injection-locked Ti:Sa laser system, seeded with cw light produced by a Ti:Sa laser system, produces pulsed light at 856 nm, which is then mixed with a 532 nm pulse, from a single longitudinal mode Nd:YVO4 laser, creating 328 nm light by a SFG process.

with a 532 nm pulse from an Nd:YVO₄ laser (PXn200-2-GF-SLM) to obtain 328 nm pulsed light. The frequency was scanned using the Matisse Commander software.

3. RESULTS

As presented in Fig. 3, laser frequency scans on the stable silver isotope ¹⁰⁹Ag were taken once with each setup, while experimental conditions were kept as similar as possible. An offset corresponding to the center of gravity (CoG) of the scanned transition is subtracted from the laser frequency to indicate the frequency detuning. The analysis was carried out using the SATLAS¹⁹ Python package, used to fit a calculated hyperfine spectrum with transition frequencies related to the HFS transition frequency given as

$$\Delta\nu = A \cdot \frac{C}{2} + B \cdot \frac{3C(C+1) - 4I(I+1)J(J+1)}{8I(2I-1)J(2J-1)} \quad (1)$$

where J is the atomic spin, I is the nuclear spin, A and B the hyperfine coupling constants, and the Casimir factor $C = F(F+1) - I(I+1) - J(J+1)$, where F is the total angular momentum. Both the atomic ground and excited state exhibit a hyperfine splitting, yielding a total of three HFS components. However, the experimentally achieved resolution allows to resolve only the larger ground state splitting into two peaks, which are separated by the A_g factor, while the excited state splitting is very small and stays unresolved, as seen in Fig. 3.

From measurements with a Fabry-Pérot interferometer (FPI) installed after the PDA, the final optical linewidth at 328 nm was calculated. Typically, the non-linearity of the piezoelectric actuators used in the FPI accounts for most of the uncertainty and was assumed to be about 10% of the absolute value. After fitting the experimental HFS spectra, the transition linewidth is calculated. Both values are presented in the table 1.

Table 1: Optical linewidth calculated from the FPI patterns and the fitted transition linewidth done with SATLAS.

Setup	Optical linewidth (MHz)	Relative error	Observed experimental linewidth (MHz)	Relative error
OPO PDA	156(17)	11%	239(14)	6%
Dye PDA	140(17)	12%	245(10)	4%
SFG	141(14)	10%	228(15)	7%

From each fit, the hyperfine splitting $\Delta\nu$ was calculated, by assuming a fixed ratio of $A_{excited}/A_{ground} = 0.0186(4)$.¹³ Results for the SFG setup were significantly affected by the unstable operation of the lasers. The mode structure of the Nd:YVO₄ laser varied erratically and uncontrollable during the laser scans, leading to the switch of modes and side peaks on the hyperfine spectrum. In table 2, the hyperfine splitting values obtained from the data analysis are listed. The OPO PDA setup agrees within 1σ and the dye PDA within 2σ . However, for the SFG, it agrees within 3σ , which can be due to the side peaks present in the spectrum that are not accounted for in the fitting model.

Table 2: Hyperfine splitting parameter A_g for ¹⁰⁹Ag from spectroscopic studies of the $5s \ ^2S_{1/2} \rightarrow 5p \ ^2P_{3/2}$ transition using the three different laser setups. The first column contains the experimental values and the last column shows the literature value.

Setup	$\Delta\nu_{exp}$ (MHz)	Relative error	$\Delta\nu_{lit}$ (MHz)
OPO PDA	-1959(21)	1.07%	
Dye PDA	-1945(22)	1.13%	1976.932075(17) ¹³
SFG	-1948(13)	0.67%	

(a) ^{109}Ag HFS obtained by fitting the data from the OPO PDA setup.

(b) ^{109}Ag HFS obtained by fitting the data from the dye PDA setup.

(c) ^{109}Ag HFS obtained by fitting the data from the SFG setup.

Figure 3: Fitted ^{109}Ag hyperfine spectrum, where the ground state hyperfine splitting can be observed.

The benchmark for the here proposed new laser system involving the cw OPO is set by comparing the calculated optical linewidth, the given transition linewidth, and finally, the resolved hyperfine splitting between each laser setup. According to the previous results, all three setups produce similar transition linewidth values within the uncertainties, regardless of the optical linewidth difference. By comparing the obtained hyperfine splitting factor A_g with the literature value, preference for the two systems using the PDA is given, while the instability of the SFG system leads to a significantly less precise result.

4. DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

Three laser systems were used to induce the first excitation step at 328 nm for high-resolution laser spectroscopy of the isotope ^{109}Ag . The optical linewidth was calculated based on FPI measurements for each laser setup. During the spectroscopy experiment, the HFS was resolved and analyzed, giving the transition linewidth and the hyperfine splitting as parameters to compare.

The new setup proposed here, deploying a cw single-mode OPO system for pulsed dye amplification, generates optical linewidths comparable to other proven laser types commonly used in high-resolution laser spectroscopy, such as cw dye lasers pulsed dye amplified and injection-locked Ti:Sa lasers. Comparing the results for the transition linewidth, the OPO performance is on the same level as the other systems. Finally, the OPO yielded equal results to the dye laser from the measured hyperfine splitting, which in turn were more favorable than the results obtained by the SFG method.

In a comparison between the different methods, the complexity of each laser setup also needs to be taken into consideration. The full solid-state composition of the SFG setup makes it the preferable choice. However, the mode-hopping nature of the high-power Nd:YVO₄ laser used here renders it difficult to obtain a stable narrow optical linewidth over long periods, which can be easily overcome through active frequency stabilization. For the dye laser, dye depletion is a pressing matter due to the extended operation periods during on-line runs of up to several days. Such a system requires regular maintenance to keep it up in stable conditions. The OPO's solid-state nature makes it advantageous over a full dye laser setup, due to the low maintenance needed and the ease of operation. Replacing the PDA stage of the OPO setup with a pulse amplification stage based on Optical Parametric Amplification (OPA) would provide a full-solid-state solution, eliminating all disadvantages of dye lasers, and would allow to cover the widest spectral range of all systems. Such a new development is planned for the near future.

In this work, it has been proven that a cw OPO system can be implemented for high-resolution spectroscopy, providing equivalent results and performances compared to dye and Ti:Sa lasers. This opens the possibility for the development of new excitation schemes with transition wavelengths, which were previously inaccessible. Alternatively, an extension towards new operational ranges for future OPO systems can be intended to access ranges of the most difficult, or even inaccessible, wavelength for dye and Ti:Sa lasers. This OPO system will be tested further and used in pursuing applications of laser spectroscopy on actinides at JGU, Mainz and ISOLDE, CERN.

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